

Factors Influencing Accessibility and Utilization of Library Resources by Nursing and Midwifery Students Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 14 February 2022	The study was conducted on factors influencing accessibility and utilization of library resources by nursing and midwifery students Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey research design. Two objectives with two corresponding research questions and two null hypotheses were used. A total of 450 students comprising of 265 student nurses and 194 student midwives were used in this study. The entire population of the study was used to take care of subject attrition. Multistage sampling procedure with appropriate techniques was used. The instrument for data collection used in this study was a structured questionnaire. Three experts validated the instrument. From the duly completed copies of the questionnaire, the required data were generated and analyzed using mean and standard deviation statistics for answering the research questions and the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for testing the hypothesis at 0.5. The findings revealed that there is accessibility of library resources among the students. The result further shows that students' utilization of library resources. Out of the twelve (12) items in the Table, eight (8) of the items were accepted by student nurses as the mostly used library resources, while four (4) of the items were accepted by student midwives as the mostly used library resources. The three items accepted by both nursing and midwifery students as the mostly used library resources include "Reference books", "Journals (hard copies)", and "Submitted (past) students' project". The study recommends that adequate computer with internet facilities and other electronic resources should be acquired and made more readily available for use by students. This is to complement the print resources which are already available in the library as well as enable the students to have access to online resources and data bases.
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INTRODUCTION

Successful educational system depends exhaustively on the accessibility and utilization of information resources and services. In this regard, school libraries, also known as academic libraries are providing knowledge and information resources for teaching, learning, and research (Yusuf, & Iwu, 2017). Libraries in the educational Institutions such as schools of Nursing and Midwifery are important to the teaching-learning process because they primarily stock materials that aid teaching and learning (Owate & Okpa-Iroha, 2015). School libraries are known as learning laboratory for the school. They provide total learning package required by the students and their teachers (Ajiboye, & Tella, 2017).

However, the ability of the academic library to provide the available learning resources is being continually undermined and called into question, especially in developing nations like Nigeria (Popoola, 2018). One of the objectives of nursing education is to encourage and motivate nursing and midwifery students to ensure the availability of library resources through a good and a lifelong study habit. To achieve this, the right information must be available for the students at the right time in its appropriate format, which is the responsibilities of the library on the other hand, the students must make use of the available resources. In spite of the fact that library is the supportive input for any academic institutions for teaching, learning and research, it is observed that various institutions are not providing adequate library

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resources for their students, and also in places where these resources are available; they are not put into maximum use by the students ((Adeoye, & Popoola, 2019).

School library is one of those resources which are essential to support and strengthen the educational quality of students. Over the centuries, School libraries are the sources of keeping and distributing the information through books, journals, maps and other resources that are used by students in their learning process (Don, 2016). The role of library in education cannot be underestimated. Libraries are in the vanguard of generation, acquisition, processing, organization and dissemination of information resources in academic institutions, in order to achieve organizational as well as national development (Oyewusi, & Oyeboade, 2019).

Concept of library use refers to the “act of using” or visiting the library, at least two to three times a week. This includes: accessing and reading the library materials such as text books, journals, newspapers, pamphlets, computers and other relevant library materials. People use the library for various reasons and to satisfy different needs. Some use the virtual library specifically to read, others use it for research, and some others use it to communicate and share information. No matter what one is using the library for, the fundamental truth is that it is information related.

According to Adeoye, and Popoola (2019), Library resources refer to everything that is used in providing the required services to the clientele. Library resource is those materials which enable libraries to carry out their function effectively. They are made up of books and other information bearing media. Library resources can be divided into groups; according to their functions, and level of scholarship, or according to their different formats. In tertiary institutions for example the resources fall into two major categories; therefore according to the level of scholarship and their function. These resources include study/teaching materials and research materials.

There are difference reasons for the uses of library. Williamson (2019) listed the specific user related characteristics or variables that have been measured to include frequency of library/information use, reasons for use, types of library/information use, attitudes and opinions regarding libraries, reading patterns, level of satisfaction, demographic data, personality, lifestyle and awareness of library services. Nursing and midwifery are among the science fields in which the expansion of information is enormous and critically dependent on up-to-date information. This dependence upon up-to-date information of the nursing education is what prompted the researchers to investigate accessibility and utilization of library resources among nursing and midwifery student in Bauchi State, Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

It is a known fact that for students to advance in the process of education there must be access to relevant information in

various formats. School library are one way to provide students with reading materials. The academic excellence of any academic institution depends on its access to quality information sources and resources. Students’ failure to use the school library and its resources to expand their study habit has a negative effect on their academic performance (Williamson, 2010). The researchers observed over the years that despite the efforts made by the Management of Schools of Nursing and Midwifery in Bauchi State to provide the library with reading materials, the students’ use of library seems to be poor, which is worrisome.

This has led to emergence of some questions as: How accessible are these services to students? To what extent do nursing and midwifery students utilize these resources? It is on these bases, it became imperative to investigate the accessibility and utilization of library resources among students of schools of nursing and midwifery in Bauchi State.

PURPOSES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this research study was to investigate the accessibility and utilization of library resources among nursing and midwifery students in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, Bauchi State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. To determine the accessibility of library resources to the nursing and midwifery students.
2. Find out the level of utilization of library resources by students.

Research Questions:

The study has attempted to answer the following research questions:

1. How accessible are the library resources to the nursing and midwifery students?
2. What is the level of utilization of library resources by the students?

Hypotheses

The Following Null Hypotheses were examined and tested during the study.

1. There is no significant difference between nursing and midwifery students in the use of library resources.
2. There is no significant difference in the use of library resources among nursing students at different class levels.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will help raise awareness of nursing and midwifery students on the availability and use of library resources and services to meet their varying information needs. The findings from the study have revealed the extent of use of library resources of students in schools of nursing and midwifery, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, Bauchi State. In addition, the study has

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produced baseline data for information pertaining to access and utilization of students of schools of nursing and midwifery in Bauchi State.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The design used in this study was descriptive cross-sectional survey method. This design was adopted, because according to Ugah, (2017), it is scientific, non-experimental method which involves observing and describing a phenomenon without influencing it in any way. The design is considered appropriate for the phenomenon being investigated that involves the appraisal of access, and utilization of school library resources among nursing and midwifery students in schools of nursing and midwifery in Bauchi State. This method was deemed fit as it was successfully used by Mubashrah, Riaz and Shaziaah, (2013) who studied library resources utilization by teachers and students.

The study was conducted in the Schools of Nursing and Midwifery, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, Bauchi State.

The schools of Nursing and Midwifery Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, were established in 1977 about a year after the creation of the State from the defunct Borno State. The programme was established based on the need of the State for improved quality nursing care and the need for professional growth and enhancement of the nurses in line with the global trend.

The population of this study consisted of all the nursing and midwifery students in schools of nursing and midwifery, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, Bauchi State. The total population was 459 students, comprising of 265 student nurses and 194 student midwives as can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Population of Students in the Schools of Nursing and Midwifery, ATBUTH Bauchi:

School	Number of Students
Nursing	265
Midwifery	194
Total	459

Source: College Record, (2013)

Due to the manageable size of the population, the entire population of 459 students was used. This was to take care of subject attrition in which some of the students may not be around during the period of data collection or unwilling to participate in the study. The inclusion criteria however included: Availability at the time of data collection; willingness to participate in the study and must be a student nurse or midwife of either of the two schools.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was questionnaire. The items in the questionnaire were generated from the literature reviewed based on the objectives set for the study to elicit information from the students on the topic

of the study. The instrument has sections A, and B. Section A comprises the respondents’ demographic characteristics, while section B contains items designed to address the research objectives, research questions and the hypotheses of the study. Items 12- 41 were presented on a 4-point Likert type scale ranging from Strongly disagree (1) to Strongly agree (4), and a 4 - point Likert type scale ranging from Not available (1) to Available and very adequate (4).

The face validity of the questionnaire was carried out by submitting the instrument to three senior lecturers in the Department of Nursing Science, University of Nigeria, and Enugu Campus. They examined the items in the instrument of data collection in line with the purpose, objectives and the hypotheses set out for the study. They also assessed the language used in developing the instrument. Necessary modifications were made and their input and suggestions were effected.

The instrument was administered once on the 10% of the population, which is 46 students; (comprising 23 student nurses and 23 student midwives) from School of Nursing and School of Midwifery Birnin Kudu, Jigawa State respectively. All items were scored in descending order of ranked value-weighted options except Items 31, 32, 34, 38 – 41 which were scored in ascending order of ranked value-weighted options. A split-half technique was used for test of reliability. A total of 46 filled pilot sample questionnaire copies were shuffled and randomly divided into two equal groups of 23 copies in each group. The two sets of data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), Item-Total statistics, inter-item correlation and Cronbach alpha statistic.

To ensure construct validity of the instrument (how well each questionnaire item measures a supposed construct), ANOVA was applied to the data. All p-values from result showed significant construct validity ($p < 0.05$). To identify any poorly constructed questionnaire items, an item-total statistic was carried out. All “*cronbach alpha values if questionnaire item was deleted*” stood at between 0.4 – 0.6, thus depicting that all questionnaire items are significantly relevant to the construct of measure. To ensure convergent validity of the instrument (how well the instrument will produce similar results if administered to student nurses or student midwives exclusively), an inter-item correlation was carried out. This yielded an inter-item correlation coefficient of 0.76, depicting convergent validity of the individual questionnaire items. To ensure overall reliability of the instrument (how consistent the entire questionnaire can measure the same latent variable), the data was subjected to cronbach alpha statistic. This yielded a cronbach alpha of 0. 84 depicting good overall reliability of the instrument.

In order to gain access to the respondents, a letter of introduction was obtained from the Head of Department of Nursing Sciences, University of Nigeria, and Enugu Campus and was presented to the respective schools. The researcher administered the copies of the questionnaire to the

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respondents with the help of four (4) research assistants who were briefed on the purpose of the study. Data collection lasted for three weeks.

The data obtained from the instrument were collated, tabulated and analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21.0. Using descriptive statistics, the frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviations. The inferential statistics - t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were employed in testing of the hypotheses at p value of .05 level of significance at a confidence interval of 95%. For the purpose of decision making, a cut-off point of 2.50 was used as the minimum value of mean in this study. For the purpose of decision making, the researcher used the interval scale of 0.5. The upper limit of 3 is 3.49 and the lower limit is 2.50. Therefore, the items with mean greater than 2.49 were accepted or considered adequate, while those with mean less than 2.50 were rejected or was considered inadequate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from data analysis with their interpretations were presented. Out of the four hundred and fifty-nine (459) copies of questionnaire administered, three hundred and ninety (390) of them were returned for analysis giving response rate of 85.0%. The mean age and standard deviation of the student nurses and midwives is 21.9±3.6years.

Demographic Characteristics of the Nursing and Midwifery Students

Descriptive statistics involving frequencies and their percentages were used to analyze data on demographic profiles of the nursing and midwifery students. The results of the analysis were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Demographic Distribution of Nursing and Midwifery Students N=390

Item	Student Nurses N=217	Student Midwives N=173	Total
Age Group in Years			
16-20years	94(43.3%)	81(46.8%)	175(44.9%)
21-25years	81(37.3%)	78(45.1%)	159(40.8%)
26-30years	33(15.2%)	12(6.9%)	45 (11.5%)
31years & above	9 (4.2%)	2 (1.2%)	11 (2.8%)
Mean age	22.3(SD=4.1)	21.6(SD=2.9)	21.9(SD=3.6)
Sex			
Male	91 (42.0%)	0 (0.0%)	91(23.3%)
Female	126 (58.0%)	173(100%)	299(76.7%)
Marital Status			
Single	168(77.4%)	115(66.5%)	283(72.6%)
Married	49 (22.6%)	57 (32.9%)	106(27.2%)
Widowed	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.3%)
Type of Student			
Basic	183(84.3%)	173(100%)	356(91.0%)
Post Basic	34(9.0%)	0 (0.0%)	34 (9.0%)
Year of Study			
First Year	136(62.7%)	108(62.4%)	244(62.6%)
Second Year	14 (6.5%)	39 (22.5%)	53 (13.6%)
Third Year	67 (30.9%)	26 (15.0%)	93 (23.8%)

The result in Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the student nurses and midwives in the study. In the age group, 175 (44.9%) of them were 16-20years, 159 (40.8%) of them were 21-25years, 45 (11.5%) of them were 26-30years, while 11 (2.8%) of them were 31years & above. Their gender showed that 91 (23.3%) of them were male, while 299 (76.7%) of them were female. As regard to their marital status, majority 283 (72.6%) of them were single, 106 (27.4%) of them were married, while only 1 (0.3%) of them

was widowed. In their type of student, 183 (84.3%) of the Student Nurses were Basic, and 34 (9.0%) of them were Post Basic; while 173 (100%) were Student Midwives. The years of study showed that 244 (62.6%) of them were first year students, 53 (13.6%) of them were second year students, while 93 (23.8%) of them were third year students.

Objective 1: To Determine the Accessibility of Library Resources to Nursing and Midwifery Students of ATBUTH, Bauchi.

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Table 3: Accessibility of Library Resources to the Nursing and Midwifery Students N=390

ITEMS	Student Nurses (N=217)						Student Midwives (N=173)					
	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Stdev	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Stdev
Only during the day times	102	68	24	23	3.15*	1.04	95	31	25	22	3.15*	1.04
Only at night times	19	18	66	114	1.68	0.98	5	5	63	100	1.62	0.81
At all times of the day	40	43	67	67	2.18	1.12	26	34	60	63	2.24	1.05
School days only	82	50	36	49	2.90*	1.11	97	30	21	25	2.94*	1.19

The result in Table 3 above shows the accessibility of library resources among the students. Out of the four (4) items in the table, only two (2) of them were accepted by nursing and midwifery students as accessibility to library resources in the schools. These items include “Only during the day times”, and “School days only”. The other two (2) items are not

accepted by both student nurses and midwives include as accessibility of library resources in their schools. These items include “Only at night times”, and “All the times of the day”.
Objective 2: To Determine the Utilization of Library Resources by the Nursing and Midwifery Students of ATBUTH, Bauchi.

Table 4: Students’ Utilization of Library Resources N=390

ITEMS	Student Nurses (N=217)						Student Midwives (N=173)					
	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Stdev	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Stdev
Text books	171	41	2	3	3.75*	0.54	128	41	2	2	3.71*	0.55
Reference books	70	115	22	10	3.13*	0.77	64	73	26	10	3.10*	0.86
Journals (hard copies)	34	116	48	19	2.76*	0.82	27	73	44	29	2.57*	0.95
News paper	35	99	65	18	2.70*	0.84	32	61	40	40	2.49	1.04
Magazines	24	93	71	29	2.52*	0.86	27	58	48	40	2.42	1.01
Online books	56	95	46	20	2.86*	0.91	15	23	68	67	1.92	0.93
Photocopying	28	43	85	61	2.18	0.98	25	27	52	69	2.05	1.07
Printing	31	54	66	66	2.23	1.04	23	25	57	68	2.02	1.04
e-mail	58	96	37	26	2.86	0.95	19	40	51	63	2.09	1.02
Audio/visual cassettes	14	34	73	96	1.84	0.92	12	21	59	81	1.79	0.91
Submitted (past) students` project	70	89	38	20	2.96*	0.93	44	67	32	30	2.72*	1.03
Internet resources and computer	95	91	22	9	3.25*	0.80	29	56	37	51	2.36	1.08

Mean score > cut – off point of 2.50

The result in Table 4 showed students’ utilization of library resources. Out of the twelve (12) items in the table, eight (8) of items were accepted by student nurses as the mostly used library resources, while four (4) of items were accepted by student midwives as the mostly used library resources. The three items accepted by both nursing and midwifery students as the mostly used library resources include “Reference books”, “Journals (hard copies)”, and “Submitted (past) students` project”. The five items accepted by student nurses only as the mostly used library resources are “Text books”,

“News Paper”, “Magazines”, “Online books”, and “Internet resources and computer”. The other four (4) items which are not accepted by both student nurses and midwives as the mostly used library resources are “Photocopying”, “Printing”, “e-mail”, and “Audio/visual cassettes”. In general, the student nurses use library resources more frequently than the student midwives since the mean and standard deviation are significant.

Hypothesis 1: There was no significant difference in the use of library resources among nursing and midwifery students.

Table 5: t-test analysis of library resources usage among student nurses and student midwives

Student	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	t-test	df	P-value
Student Nurse	217	2.75	0.49	5.879	388	0.000*
Student Midwives	173	2.44	0.57			

Table 5 above shows the t-test analysis of library resources usage among student nurses and student midwives. Hypothesis 2 is rejected (P<0.05) because it revealed that

there is significant difference in the use of library resources among student nurses and student midwives. This implies that

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the student nurses have good usage of library resources than the student midwives.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the use of library resources among nursing students at different class level

Table 6: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of use of library resources among student nurses at different class level

Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between Groups	1.000	2	0.500	2.072	0.128
Within Groups	51.637	214	0.241		
Total	52.637	216			

Table 6 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of use of library resources among student nurses at different class level. Hypothesis 4 is accepted ($P > 0.05$) as it revealed that there is no significant difference in the use of library resources among student nurses at different class level.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study were discussed in line with the specific objectives, research questions and hypotheses of the study.

Accessibility of Library Resources to the Nursing and Midwifery Students

The result in Table 2 shows the accessibility of library resources among the students. Out of the four (4) items in the Table, only two (2) of them were accepted by nursing and midwifery students as accessibility of library resources in their schools (mean scores > cut-off point of 2.50). These items include “Only during the day times”, and “School day only”. The other two (2) items were not accepted by both student nurses and student midwives as accessibility of library resources in their schools (mean scores < cut-off point of 2.50). These items include “Only at night times”, and “All the times of the day”.

The findings of this study is in congruent with the findings of Ajayi (2014) who conducted a study at Ladoke Akintola University, Ogbomoso Nigeria to investigate the accessibility and use of library resources by undergraduates. Their Results indicated that Nigerian students perceive library as a place where only serious academic work can be done.

This finding agrees with the findings of Muhammad and Iyoro (2015) whom observed that information availability does not mean accessibility and use and that academic libraries should stimulate primary demand for their products and services. This view also is upheld by Mason (2010), who opines that librarians must be sympathetic and helpful to all students on the one hand and that on the other hand, students must be aware that librarians and faculty members are there to instruct and encourage their intellectual odyssey and should be seen as facilitators.

Utilization of Library Resources by the Nursing and Midwifery Students

The result in Table 3 showed students’ utilization of library resources. Out of the twelve (12) items in the Table, eight (8)

of the items were accepted by student nurses as the mostly used library resources, while four (4) of the items were accepted by student midwives as the mostly used library resources. The three items accepted by both nursing and midwifery students as the mostly used library resources include “Reference books”, “Journals (hard copies)”, and “Submitted (past) students` project”.

This finding is in congruence with the findings of Gunasekera (2020) in his study on “Students Usage of an academic Library: a user survey conducted at the Main Library University of Peradeni.” Who explored that library resources and services are not being fully utilized by undergraduates.

These findings are in congruence with the findings of Akin & Ajayi (2014) while studying the use of Federal University of Technology Library in Nigeria equally found out that out of 475 students, only 82 use the library on daily basis. A similar study by Mubashrah, Tariq, and Shazia (2018) also revealed that students use the library mostly during examinations to study and to do class assignments.

However, these findings are not consistent with the findings of Moses and Popoola (2017)) in their statistical study in Covenant University where students utilized the online public access catalogue more than the manual catalogue. In related studies, Onuoha, Ikonne. and Madukoma (2016) while studying library use and research productivity of postgraduate students, concluded that postgraduate students place more importance on books (print) followed closely by internet provision and electronic journals. Lohar, & Kumbar (2017) compared the use of library resources between students at Imo State University and AlvanIkoku Federal College of Education. They grouped library materials into three broad categories namely: oral information; printed information and digitised information. The study established that in both libraries, students utilised printed information more than digitized information and oral information was never used in any of the libraries. The study also identified insufficient library space as the greatest problem facing the use of both libraries.

Hypothesis 01: There is no significant difference in the use of library resources among nursing and midwifery students Table 4: t-test analysis of library resources usage among student nurses and student midwives. Hypothesis 2 is rejected ($P < 0.05$) because it revealed that there is significant difference in the use of library resources among student

nurses and student midwives. This implies that the student nurses have good usage of library resources than the student midwives. Hypothesis 2 is rejected ($P < 0.05$) and therefore concluded that there is significant difference in the use of library resources among student nurses and midwives. This implies that the student nurses have good usage of library resources than the student midwives.

The result above signifies that differences exist between the students with regard to the use of library resources in schools of nursing and midwifery ATBUTH, Bauchi.

Hypothesis 02: There will be no significant difference in the use of library resources among nursing students at different class level

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the use of library resources among student nurses at different class level In general, the First year nursing students use the library resources (mean score 2.80 and standard deviation 0.52) more than the senior ones. Hypothesis 3 is accepted ($P > 0.05$) and therefore concluded that there is no significant difference in the use of library resources among student nurses at different class level.

The results above indicate that there is no difference among nursing students at different class level with regard to the use of library resources in schools of nursing and midwifery ATBUTH, Bauchi.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINDINGS

1. It was also discovered in this study that the student nurses and the student midwives have access to the library only on school days and only during the day times. Consequently, the library books are not lent to the students especially to the midwifery students on requests. The implication of all these is that these will limit the reading habit of the students and will also affect the semester, session or even the final year results of the students.
2. Lack of e-library, more especially in the school of midwifery limits access to current educational materials by the students. Hence, this implies that the students will be lagging behind in the present information technology and at any stage in their studies.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are made;

The results of this study revealed that out of 459 respondents; only 243 respondents utilize the library resources. Of this figure, student nurses utilize the school library more than their counter parts in the school of midwifery. Specifically, 76.5% of the student nurses utilize the school library as compared to 44.5% of the student midwives.

Lack of e-library resources appeared to be the main challenges of both the nursing and midwifery students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Adequate computer with internet facilities and other electronic resources should also be acquired and made more readily available for use by students. This is to complement the print resources which are already available in the library as well as enable the students to have access to online resources and data bases.
1. Library hours should be increased to give more chance to students to patronize the library resources.
2. The authority concerned should provide enough funds for the school library management so that the libraries could provide adequate resources and services like internet services, audio- visual materials, online public access catalogue (OPAC) among others. at all times.

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